

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Project Acronym: **ERIGrid 2.0**

Project Number: **870620**

Periodic Technical Report

Part B

0th Periodic Report

Period Covered by the Report: dd/mm/yyyy to dd/mm/yyyy

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Beneficiary in Charge: AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)

Report Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Report Number:	0
Report Full Title:	Periodic Technical Report
Report Short Title:	Periodic Report
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-0-PeriodicReport-draft-vn.n
Beneficiary in Charge:	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)
Report Version:	vn.n
Contractual Date:	dd/mm/yyyy
Report Submission Date:	dd/mm/yyyy
Lead Author(s):	[Names of co-authors (partners short names)]
Co-author(s):	[Names of co-authors (partners short names)]
Status:	<u>x</u> draft, __ final, __ submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
dd/mm/yyyy	v1.0	Name (Partner short name)	Draft report template

Table of Contents

1. Explanation of the Work carried out by the Beneficiaries and Overview of the Progress	7
1.1 Objectives	7
1.2 Explanation of the Work Carried per Work Package	7
1.3 Impact	10
1.4 Access Provisions to Research Infrastructures.....	10
1.5 Resources used to provide Access to Research Infrastructures.....	12
2. Update of the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results	13
3. Update of the Data Management Plan	14
4. Follow-up of Recommendations and Comments from Previous Review(s).....	15
5. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2	16
5.1 Tasks	16
5.2 Use of Resources	16
References	17
Appendix A. Document Guidelines	18
A.1. Report Titles.....	18
A.2. File Naming.....	18
A.3. Change Log	18
A.4. Document Formatting.....	19
A.5. Language and Notation	21
A.6. L ^A T _E X Style Files	22
A.7. Formatting Bibliographical References	23
A.8. Associated Outputs.....	23
Appendix B. Heading	25
B.1. Heading.....	25
B.2. Heading.....	25
Appendix C. Heading	26
C.1. Heading	26
C.2. Heading	26

List of Figures

Figure 1: Caption caption caption caption caption caption caption caption. (a) Caption caption caption, (b) Caption caption caption, (c) Caption caption caption..... 20

List of Tables

Table 1: Summary of properties of different modelling formalisms. The table below is inserted as graphic.....	20
Table 2: Summary of properties of different modelling formalisms. The table below is produced using \LaTeX 's table environment.	20

List of Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
OA	Open Access
RI	Research Infrastructure
RP	Reporting Period
PM	Person Month
TA	Trans-national Access Activities
VA	Virtual Access Activities
WP	Work Package

1 Explanation of the Work carried out by the Beneficiaries and Overview of the Progress

This section summarises the work carried out by the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium during the 0th Reporting Period (RP) towards the project goals and work plan as described in the Grant Agreement (GA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019).

1.1 Objectives

TODO: “List the specific objectives for the project as described in Section 1.1 of the Description of Action (DoA) and described the work carried out during the reporting period towards the achievement of each listed objective. Provide clear and measurable details.”

1.2 Explanation of the Work Carried per Work Package

This section provides an overview of the work carried out and results achieved per Work Package (WP) during the the 0th Reporting Period.

1.2.1 Work Package WP01

Overview and Goals

<i>Work Package Summary</i>							
<i>WP No.</i>	01	<i>Title of WP</i>	WP Title				
<i>Start</i>	Mxx	<i>End</i>	Myy				
<i>Participating Organisations</i>							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP Leader: Partner 1 • Participants: Partner 2, Partner 3, Partner 4, Partner 5, Partner 6, Partner 7 							
<i>Goals</i>							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal 1 • Goal 2 • Goal 3 							
<i>Participant number</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<i>Participant short name</i>	Partner 1	Partner 2	Partner 3	Partner 4	Partner 5	Partner 6	Partner 7
<i>PM per participant</i>	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx

Status

TODO: “Briefly explain the status of the WP.”

Progress per Task

Task no: title (Month xx-yy)

TODO: “Briefly explain the progress of the task in context to the DoA.”

Task no: title (Month xx-yy)

TODO: “Briefly explain the progress of the task in context to the DoA.”

Main Results and Achievements

TODO: “Briefly summarise the main results and achievements of the WP in context of the DoA.”

Deviations and Corrective Actions

TODO: “Briefly summarise any deviations and performed corrective actions of the WP in context of the DoA.”

1.2.2 Work Package WP02**Overview and Goals**

Work Package Summary							
<i>WP No.</i>	02	<i>Title of WP</i>	WP Title				
<i>Start</i>	Mxx	<i>End</i>	Myy				
<i>Participating Organisations</i>							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP Leader: Partner 1 • Participants: Partner 2, Partner 3, Partner 4, Partner 5, Partner 6, Partner 7 							
<i>Goals</i>							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal 1 • Goal 2 • Goal 3 							
<i>Participant number</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<i>Participant short name</i>	Partner 1	Partner 2	Partner 3	Partner 4	Partner 5	Partner 6	Partner 7
<i>PM per participant</i>	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx

Status

TODO: “Briefly explain the status of the WP.”

Progress per Task**Task no: title (Month xx-yy)**

TODO: “Briefly explain the progress of the task in context to the DoA.”

Task no: title (Month xx-yy)

TODO: “Briefly explain the progress of the task in context to the DoA.”

Main Results and Achievements

TODO: “Briefly summarise the main results and achievements of the WP in context of the DoA.”

Deviations and Corrective Actions

TODO: “Briefly summarise any deviations and performed corrective actions of the WP in context of the DoA.”

1.2.3 Work Package WPxy**Overview and Goals**

<i>Work Package Summary</i>							
<i>WP No.</i>	xy	<i>Title of WP</i>	WP Title				
<i>Start</i>	Mxx	<i>End</i>	Myy				
<i>Participating Organisations</i>							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP Leader: Partner 1 • Participants: Partner 2, Partner 3, Partner 4, Partner 5, Partner 6, Partner 7 							
<i>Goals</i>							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal 1 • Goal 2 • Goal 3 							
<i>Participant number</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<i>Participant short name</i>	Partner 1	Partner 2	Partner 3	Partner 4	Partner 5	Partner 6	Partner 7
<i>PM per participant</i>	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx	xx

Status

TODO: “Briefly explain the status of the WP.”

Progress per Task**Task no: title (Month xx-yy)**

TODO: “Briefly explain the progress of the task in context to the DoA.”

Task no: title (Month xx-yy)

TODO: “Briefly explain the progress of the task in context to the DoA.”

Main Results and Achievements

TODO: “Briefly summarise the main results and achievements of the WP in context of the DoA.”

Deviations and Corrective Actions

TODO: “Briefly summarise any deviations and performed corrective actions of the WP in context of the DoA.”

1.3 Impact

TODO: “Include in this section whether the information on section 2.1 of the DoA (how your project will contribute to the expected impacts) is still relevant or needs to be updated. Include further details in the latter case.”

1.4 Access Provisions to Research Infrastructures

1.4.1 Trans-national Access Activities

Description of the publicity concerning the new opportunities for access

TODO: “In the first periodic report describe the measures taken to publicise to research teams throughout Europe the opportunities for access open to them under the GA. In the following periodic reports indicate only additional measures and changes.”

Description of the selection process

TODO: “In the first periodic report, describe the procedure used to select users: organisation of the Selection Panel, any additional selection criteria employed by the Selection Panel, measures to promote equal opportunities, etc. Specify if feedback is given to rejected applicants and in which form. In the following periodic reports indicate only changes to the existing procedure.”

The list of the Selection Panel members should be maintained and update when necessary in order to prove that the panel is composed following the conditions indicated in Article 16.1 of the GA. The Commission reserves the right to request this list at any time.

Indicate number, date and venue (if not carried out remotely) of the meetings of the Selection panel during the reporting period.

Provide integrated information on the selection of user projects and on the scientific output of supported users. In particular indicate the number of eligible User projects submitted in the reporting period and the number of the selected ones taking into account only calls for which the selection has been completed in the reporting period. Indicate also the number of user projects, started and supported in the reporting period, which have a majority of users not working in an European Union (EU) or associated country.”

Description of Trans-national Access Activities (TA)

TODO: “Give an overview of the user-projects and users supported in the reporting period indicating their number, their scientific fields and other relevant information you may want to

highlight. You should maintain the list of the user-projects for which costs have been incurred in the reporting period. A user-project can run over more than one reporting period. In this case it should be inserted in the list of each concerned reporting period.

The list of user-projects must include, for each user-project, the acronym, objectives, as well as the amount of access granted to it on each installation used by the user-project in the reporting period. When the user-project is completed in the reporting period the list should also include a short description of the work carried out. The Commission reserves the right to request this list at any time.

In addition you must fill the following tables (in Part A to be filled in the IT tool):

- List of users: Researchers who have access to Research Infrastructures (RIs)/installations (one or more) through Union support under the grant either in person (through visit) or through remote access;
- RIs made accessible to all researchers in Europe and beyond through EU support and summary of trans-national access provision per installation per reporting period indicate for each installation providing trans-national access under the project the quantity of access actually provided in the Reporting Period (expressed in the unit of access defined in Annex 1 for that specific installation).

”

Scientific output of the users at the facilities

TODO: “Give highlights of important research results from the user-projects supported under the grant agreement. Indicate the number and the type of publications derived by user-projects supported under the grant taking into account only publications that acknowledge the support of this EU grant.

You should maintain a list of publications that have appeared in journals (or conference proceedings) during the reporting period and are resulting from work carried out under the TA activity. List only publications that acknowledge the support of the European Community. For each publication indicate: the acronyms of the user-projects that have led to the publication itself, the authors, the title, the year of publication, the type of publication (Article in journal, Publication in conference proceeding/workshop, Book/Monograph, Chapters in book, Thesis/dissertation, whether it has been peer-reviewed or not, the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the publication references, and whether the publication is available under Open Access (OA) or not. The Commission reserves the right to request this list at any time. ”

User meetings

TODO: “If any user meetings have been organised in the reporting period, indicate for each of them the date, the venue, the number of users attending the meeting and the overall number of attendees.”

1.4.2 Virtual Access Activities

TODO: “Provide statistics on the Virtual Access Activities (VA) in the period by each installation, including quantity, geographical distribution of users and, whenever possible, information/statistics on scientific outcomes (publications, patents, etc.) acknowledging the use of the infrastructure.

As indicated in Art. 16.2, the access providers must have the VA services assessed periodically by a board composed of international experts in the field, at least half of whom must be independent from the beneficiaries. In the first periodic report, describe how the virtual access providers will comply with this obligation. In the following periodic reports indicate only changes to the existing procedure.

When an assessment is scheduled under the reporting period, the assessment report must be submitted as deliverable. ”

1.5 Resources used to provide Access to Research Infrastructures

TODO: “For virtual or trans-national access costs reported as actual costs include, for each access provider, information on how many of the Person Months (PMs) reported in the use of resources linked to the financial statements have been used to provide access and explain for which task (e.g. scientific support to users, . . .).

Information on individual subcontracts must be reported in the use of resources linked to the financial statements in the IT tool. Please mention in the comments field of each subcontract whether it is related to VA or TA. In addition, all other direct costs items related to virtual or trans-national access must be detailed in the use of resources linked to the financial statements in the IT tool, even if they do not exceed 15% of personnel costs.”

2 Update of the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

TODO: “Include in this section whether the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results as described in the DoA needs to be updated and give details.”

3 Update of the Data Management Plan

TODO: “Include in this section whether the Data Management Plan (DMP) as described in the DoA needs to be updated and give details.”

4 Follow-up of Recommendations and Comments from Previous Review(s)

TODO: “Include in this section the list of recommendations and comments from previous reviews and give information on how they have been followed up.”

5 Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2

5.1 Tasks

TODO: “Include explanations for tasks not fully implemented, critical objectives not fully achieved and/or not being on schedule. Explain also the impact on other tasks on the available resources and the planning.”

5.2 Use of Resources

TODO: “Include explanations on deviations of the use of resources between actual and planned use of resources in Annex 1, especially related to PMs per WP.

Include explanations on transfer of costs categories (if applicable).

Include explanations on adjustments to previous financial statements (if applicable).”

5.2.1 Unforeseen Subcontracting

TODO: “Specify in this section:

- the work (the tasks) performed by a subcontractor which may cover only a limited part of the project;
- explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for a subcontract, taking into account the specific characteristics of the project;
- the confirmation that the subcontractor has been selected ensuring the best value for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price and avoiding any conflict of interests.

”

5.2.2 Unforeseen use of in Kind Contribution from Third Party against Payment or Free of Charges

TODO: “Specify in this section:

- the identity of the third party;
- the resources made available by the third party respectively against payment or free of charges
- explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for using these resources for carrying out the work.

”

References

ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement. (2019). European Commission.

Lamport, L. (1994). *Latex: a document preparation system: user's guide and reference manual.* Addison-Wesley.

Tan, P.-N., Kumar, V., & Srivastava, J. (2004). Selecting the right objective measure for association analysis. *Information Systems*, 29(4), 293–313.

Appendix A. Document Guidelines

A.1. Report Titles

Deliverables have a title that is defined in the DoA. This title is referred to as the full title of the deliverable. Please stick to the official spelling. It has turned out useful to also have a short title (max 60 characters) for each deliverable, as it can be cumbersome if one always has to use the full title.

A.2. File Naming

The project will generate many documents (deliverable reports) and versions of these reports. It is beneficial to consistently use an agreed file naming format.

ERIGrid2-Dnn-ShortTitle-Status-vn.n.Extension

- Notice the hyphen between the various elements of the file name.
- **ERIGrid 2.0:** Each ERIGrid 2.0 report should be preceded by the project acronym. Notice, there is only one correct spelling of the acronym: 'ERIGrid 2.0'.
- **Dn.n:** Indicates the deliverable identifier, e.g., 'D34' for 'D3.4' following the numbering of the DoA (Part A of Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement). Notice, there is no dot between the two parts of the deliverable number.
- **ShortTitle:** This should be based on the formal short title of deliverables but 'contracted' into a single (no spaces) character string using Java class naming convention, e.g., 'ExploitationPlan', or 'ProjectWebSite'. Avoid underscore, space and other unusual characters.
- **Status:**
 - *draft* = Draft Version – indicates that the drafting of the report is in progress;
 - *final* = Final Version as checked and updated by the reviewers/WP leader/quality manager;
 - *submitted* = submitted version as submitted to the EC by the project coordinator/administrator.
- **vn.n:** The version of the report starting from v1.0.
- **Extension:** File extension, e.g., 'docx' for Microsoft Word and 'pdf' for Portable Document Format.

Examples:

- ERIGrid2-D82-InternalCommunication-draft-v1.0.docx
- ERIGrid2-D84-QualityAssurancePlan-submitted.pdf

A.3. Change Log

The Change Log is there to keep track of the changes made to the document. Whenever changes are made to the document, a new version should be created and the changes should

be briefly summarised in the Change Log. We anticipate a minimum of three phases of Change Log entries. (1) The researcher responsible for the given Deliverable enters the changes as he/she develops the document. (2) The two reviewers register the changes made in the quality assurance phase. Once the responsible researcher passes the report on to the Project Coordinator, the status should be changed from 'draft' to 'final'. (3) The Project Coordinator submits the report to the EC, the status should be changed from 'final' to 'submitted'.

A.4. Document Formatting

A.4.1. Headings

Like in many journals and books, it is a good practice not to use more than 3 levels of headings. If you really need more, then by all means do so, but you may first consider how to structure the document with a maximum of three heading levels.

Use the following capitalisation style for all headings: All terms should be capitalised and do not use a full stop at the end.

A.4.2. Captions and Citations

Use the following for captions and cross referencing:

- 'Table 1' for tables, not 'table 1' or 'Tab. 1', etc.
- 'Figure 1' for figures, not 'figure 1' or 'Fig. 1', etc.
- 'Section 1.1.1' to cross-reference other sections, not 'section 1.1.1' or 'S. 1.1.1', etc.

Do not abbreviate the word 'Equation' to 'eq', 'Eqn', etc.

Table captions should be placed above the table and figure captions should be placed below the figure. The captions should succinctly describe the content of the table or figure.

A.4.3. Tables

Producing informative tables is not easy. Avoid grid lines around each table cells (typical for people with little experience in drafting technical papers). The table below (Table 1) is a good example how tables should look like. Make sure that caption appears on the same page as the table. The table caption is above the table!

The table caption should follow the sentence style layout and end with a full stop. The caption as well as the table should be centred.

Each table must be introduced in the deliverable text. Make sure that cross references to tables are correct before submitting the deliverable.

The same (simplified) table using the \LaTeX table feature is shown below (Table 2).

A.4.4. Figures

Good figures/diagrams are even more difficult to produce than tables. Figures should contain legends explaining the symbols in the figure. Avoid surrounding the figure with a box outline.

Table 1: Summary of properties of different modelling formalisms. The table below is inserted as graphic.

	Static (s), dynamic (d)	Discrete (d), continuous (c)	Deterministic (d), stochastic (s)	Qualitative (ql), quantitative (qn)	Coarse (c), average (a), fine (f) grained
DG	s		d	ql	c
BYN	s ^a	d,c	s	qn	c
BNN	d	d	d	ql	c
GLN	d	d	d	ql	a
NLDE	d	c	d	qn	a,f
PLDE	d	c	d	ql,qn ^c	a
QDE	d	d	d	ql	a,f
PDE	d	c ^b	d	qn	a,f
SME	d	d	s	qn	f
R	d	d	d	ql	a,f

^aGeneralization to dynamic Boolean networks is possible.

^bSpatial dimension is often discretized.

^cQualitative analysis of models is possible.

Table 2: Summary of properties of different modelling formalisms. The table below is produced using L^AT_EX's table environment.

	Static	Discrete	Deterministic	Qualitative	Coarse
DG	s		d	ql	c
BYN	s	d,c	s	qn	c
BNN	d	d	d	ql	c
GLN	d	c	d	qn	a,f

If there are different parts of a figure (e.g., (a), (b), (c)), indicate these clearly. Make sure that the labels within a figure/diagram are spelled consistently within the figure/diagram and are also consistently spelled in the text. Make sure that caption appears on the same page as the figure. The figure caption is below the figure. See an example of a figure and its caption below (Figure 1).

Each figure must be introduced in the deliverable text. Make sure that cross references to figures are correct before submitting the deliverable.

The figure caption should follow the sentence style layout and end with a full stop. The figure caption as well as the figure should be centred.

Figure 1: Caption caption caption caption caption caption caption caption caption. (a) Caption caption caption, (b) Caption caption caption, (c) Caption caption caption.

A.4.5. Footnotes

This¹ is a footnote.

A.5. Language and Notation

There are a few things we should consider when writing documents in terms of language. The question is not deeply philosophical in the sense of whether one or the other approach is fundamentally correct (or wrong). It is more the case of maintaining a certain level of consistency across the project.

Since British/UK English is the official version of English within the EC, we should by default use UK English spelling (and adopt a spell-checker set to UK English). Nevertheless, US spelling is also fine – the main issue to ensure is to be consistent within a given deliverable.

Quotation marks. UK English (unlike US), use single quotation marks ('X') instead of double quotation marks ("X"). At least maintain consistency within a document.

- It is claimed that Y is 'superior' to X.
- 'Good morning, Dave,' greeted HAL.

Do not use quotation marks to indicate emphasis – use italics, bold or underline style instead.

The accepted standard for separating orders of magnitude in large figures is not ', ' or "' (quotation mark) or '.', but a non-breaking (small) space.

- This is inappropriate: 1,000,000 or 1.000.000 or 1'000'000 (very bad!)
- This is good: 1 000 000.

Capitalisation. Use capitalisation according to English grammar rules. If someone is interested, see capitalisation rules:²

Tense. Use past tense when describing activities and tasks (experiments, developments, etc) carried out in the past.

- A test bed was set up to ...
- The evaluation revealed that ...

Use present tense when describing the ideas, design, systems, etc. that exist in the present.

- The system supports the following exchange formats ...
- A key property of the system is its ability to ...

Large numbers. Use explicit format or scientific notation for large numbers

- Use 1 200 000 000, not 1.2bn or 1,200,000,000
- Or use 1.20×10^9 or 1.20×10^9

¹The footnote is at the bottom of the same page where the footnote is cited and the font size is only 9 pt. Footnotes are useful to for including nasty-looking long Web references which would look terrible if used in the main flow of the text.

²<http://andromeda.rutgers.edu/~jlynch/Writing/c.html>, <http://www.grammarbook.com/punctuation/capital.asp>

Small numbers. As usual, unless in tables and similar elements, use one, two, ... , twelve for numbers < 13 , and 13, 14, ..., for large numbers.

Numbers and units. Use small space (In \LaTeX : `\smallspace` or `\small`) to separate figures from units. E.g.,

- 10 GB, not 10GB
- 2.13 s not 2.13s

Bits, bytes and pieces. Use the following terms and abbreviations for bytes (sometimes it is better to use the full term than the abbreviation).

Bits:

kb or Kb	kilobit	10 ³
Mb	megabit	10 ⁶
Gb	gigabit	10 ⁹
Tb	terabit	10 ¹²

Bytes:

kB or KB	kilobyte	10 ³
MB	megabyte	10 ⁶
GB	gigabyte	10 ⁹
TB	terabyte	10 ¹²

Number of decimals. When a number is expressed in the scientific notation, the number of significant digits (or significant figures) is the number of digits needed to express the number to within the uncertainty of calculation. For example, if a quantity is known to be 1.234 ± 0.002 , four figures would be significant³.

Unless there is a good reason, do not use more than three fractional digits or places (the number of digits following the point).

Other issues. Avoid overly long sentences. Certain rules suggest that sentence over approximately 20 words become difficult to understand and should therefore be avoided.

A.6. \LaTeX Style Files

To use the latex template, copy the contents of this directory and use `template.tex` as the master file of your deliverable (after renaming it as required). The necessary files are:

- `erigrid2.sty`
- `istcover.sty`
- `istprog.sty`
- `graphics/`
 - `erigrid2-coverbkg.pdf`
 - `erigrid2-logo.pdf`
 - `erigrid2-partners.pdf`

Use the following macros to populate the tables on the cover and on page two:

³<http://mathworld.wolfram.com/SignificantDigits.html>

Description	URL	Availability
My Dataset 1	http://hdl.handle.net/12345	Public (Apache 2.0)
My Dataset 2	http://hdl.handle.net/54321	Private (consortium only)
My Code	github.com/erigrad2/xxx	Public (GPL3)

Appendix B. Heading

B.1. Heading

TODO: “Explain the content of the appendix.”

B.2. Heading

TODO: “Explain the content of the appendix.”

Appendix C. Heading

C.1. Heading

TODO: "Explain the content of the appendix."

C.2. Heading

TODO: "Explain the content of the appendix."

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Copyright Notice

© 2021 by the authors, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium.

